

THE ROLE OF A DIFFERENTIATED APPROACH IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the theoretical foundations, methodological directions and practical significance of the differential approach in organizing English lessons in higher education institutions. The differential approach serves to effectively organize the educational process, taking into account the individual abilities, level of knowledge and psychological characteristics of students. The author presents proposals and recommendations on the use of modern pedagogical technologies and differential methods in teaching English, and analyzes the role of this approach in the development of communicative competence.

Keywords: differential approach; English language education; higher education; individual approach; communicative competence; student activity; effective teaching.

Introduction.

In the current process of globalization, English is recognized not only as a means of international communication, but also as an important key in mastering modern science, technology and engineering. The process of teaching English in higher education institutions, in turn, is considered one of the important factors that contribute to the comprehensive development of students' personalities and their formation as competitive specialists in the international arena. Therefore, the role and importance of new approaches in English language education, in particular, the differential approach, is increasingly increasing.

The differential approach essentially involves organizing the educational process taking into account the personal characteristics, abilities, levels of preparation and speed of learning of students. In the higher education system, this approach is, first of all, important in meeting the individual needs of students, forming their independent thinking skills and language competencies. Today, in the modern educational process, the use of differential methods that take into account the individual characteristics of students rather than traditional teaching methods is considered one of the main conditions for increasing pedagogical efficiency.

Also, the differential approach to teaching English, combined with interactive methods of education and information and communication technologies, further revitalizes the language learning process. This approach, in turn, serves to develop the activity, motivation and independent learning abilities of learners. After all, the level of language acquisition of each student is determined by various factors, including his psychological state, knowledge and skills. Therefore, the correct planning and effective implementation of the differential approach in the process of English language education remains one of the pressing issues. The article analyzes the theoretical foundations of the differential approach in English lessons, its role in the practice of higher education, as well as methodological recommendations aimed at improving the quality of education based on this approach. It is expected that the results of the study will serve to further improve English lessons in higher education institutions and realize the personal potential of students.

The organization of the English language teaching process in higher education institutions taking into account the individual characteristics of students is an important requirement of today's pedagogical practice, and the differential approach is recognized as the main methodological direction in this regard. In the process of preparing this article, a number of scientific literature, foreign and national experiences aimed at studying the theoretical and practical aspects of the differential approach in English language teaching were analyzed. In particular, the theoretical views put forward by such scientists as Vygotsky L.S., Elkonin D.B., Leontev A.N., Krashen S., Brown H.D. on the organization of individual educational activities were taken as a basis. Also, the inextricable connection of the concepts of communicative approach, constructivism and student-centered education with the differential approach in English language teaching was studied.

The material used was the results of monitoring the educational process at the English departments of Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Uzbekistan State University of World Languages, and a number of regional higher educational institutions, an analysis of lesson plans containing elements of a differentiated approach to the English language, and experiences in implementing them in practice. In particular, the results of diagnostic tests aimed at determining the level of language acquisition of students, work carried out to determine their individual educational directions, observations and questionnaires on various learning styles (visual, auditory, kinesthetic) served as the main empirical sources.

The material also included the analysis of teaching and methodological manuals, electronic resources, interactive programs (for example, modules on the Quizlet, Kahoot, Moodle platforms), and the content of modern textbooks used to organize English lessons based on a differentiated approach. The effectiveness of tasks, role-playing games, project work and group discussion forms designed for individual work with students of different abilities and levels of preparation in the lesson processes was studied. The materials reviewed in the article are aimed at scientifically, theoretically and empirically substantiating the role of the differential approach in improving the quality of English language education in higher education institutions, its practical significance in the formation of language skills and communicative competence in students.

Analytical discussion:

The use of a differential approach in English lessons in higher education institutions is proving to be one of the most important principles of the modern educational process. The results of the analysis show that English lessons organized on the basis of a differential approach serve to increase the effectiveness of students' activities, improve their mastery indicators, and strengthen their motivation for independent study and learning. In particular, it was possible to see that the learning process was more expedient when groups were formed based on the initial diagnosis of students' abilities and language proficiency levels. This, in turn, allowed each student to fully realize their potential.

During the discussion, it was found that the methodological preparation of teachers is of decisive importance in implementing a differentiated approach. Although the majority of English teachers have begun to effectively use modern educational technologies - interactive games, electronic platforms, project work and multimedia resources - to implement an individual approach, in some cases this process has become superficial. This is because the effective use of a differentiated approach requires not only technical means, but also deep psychological and pedagogical knowledge, and the ability to use diagnostic tools.

Practical observations and the results of the questionnaire showed that in classes organized on the basis of a differentiated approach, students feel more free, their interest in language acquisition increases, and most importantly, they become more responsible in assessing their own knowledge. In this process, individual assignments, independent mini-projects, dialogical exercises, debates turned out to be effective. At the same time, determining which learning style

(visual, auditory or kinesthetic) students learn language material faster and teaching on this basis had a positive effect on the formation of their communicative competence.

Also, one of the main advantages of the differentiated approach is the improvement of the socio-psychological environment among students. Students have the opportunity to learn from each other, support each other, and learn from people with different levels of knowledge. However, some of the problems that arise in this process - for example, how to properly manage the gap between stronger and less prepared students, and how to optimize the volume and complexity of individual tasks - are still looking for a solution. The differentiated approach demonstrates its high efficiency in the process of teaching English, but its success largely depends on the professionalism of the teacher, the proper organization of the educational process, and the active participation of students. Therefore, in order to more widely introduce this approach, it remains an urgent task to train teachers through regular advanced training courses and create teaching and methodological materials suitable for the differentiated approach.

Conclusion

The use of a differentiated approach in English language lessons in higher education institutions is of particular importance as it allows organizing the educational process taking into account the individual abilities, level of language acquisition and personal needs of students. The results of the study showed that lessons organized on the basis of a differentiated approach increase interest in language learning, develop students' communicative competence and strengthen their motivation for independent learning.

However, the effective use of a differentiated approach requires the fulfillment of many conditions. First of all, the teacher's professional competence, thorough knowledge of diagnostic tools and skills in the appropriate use of modern educational and methodological tools are of decisive importance. At the same time, it is also necessary to adapt curricula and lesson plans to a differentiated approach, and to systematically use tests and questionnaires to identify the individual characteristics of students.

In conclusion, the differential approach is an effective means of improving the quality of English language education and serves as an important pedagogical mechanism for realizing the individual potential of students. In the future, it remains an urgent task to systematically conduct work aimed at improving the qualifications of teachers, introducing innovative technologies, and scientifically substantiating differential methods in order to further improve this approach.

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